

Simultaneous oxidation and reduction of GO and KMnO₄ for synthesis of RGO-Mn₃O₄ hybrid electrode material for supercapacitor application

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Abstract

RGO-Mn₃O₄ was synthesized through reflux method. Structural, morphological and electrochemical studies were carried out using XRD, FT-IR, SEM, micro-Raman, cyclic voltammetry, galvanostatic charge/discharge and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. RGO-Mn₃O₄ had a maximum specific capacitance of 158 Fg⁻¹ in 1 M Na₂SO₄ electrolyte at the scan rate of 5mVs⁻¹. The prepared electrode has >100% specific capacitance retention and Coulombic efficiency even after 3000 cycles at 10 Ag⁻¹. The electrochemical performance confirmed that the RGO-Mn₃O₄ composite has the positive synergistic effects between RGO and Mn₃O₄. The as-prepared RGO-Mn₃O₄ composite can be used as a hybrid electrode in electrochemical energy storage applications.

Keyword: cyclic voltammetry (CV), specific capacitance, reduced graphene oxide (RGO), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS).

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